

***Iberozospeum goliath* n. sp. (Gastropoda: Eupulmonata: Ellobiidae), the first subfossil and (supposedly) extinct species of the genus**

***Iberozospeum goliath* n. sp. (Gastropoda: Eupulmonata: Ellobiidae), la primera especie subfósil y (supuestamente) extinta del género**

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urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:8E7D17DE-4EE9-4FAC-B8ED-010E081A4ED2

Recibido el 18-II-2025. Aceptado el 26-IV-2025

ABSTRACT

The genus *Iberozospeum* Jochum, Kneubühler, Prieto & Neubert, 2022 includes nine Iberian species, all of them extant and sequenced, although phylogenetic analyses suggest the existence of more than 20 potentially taxonomically recognizable lineages. Apart from these populations, in the El Refugio-3 cave (Trucíos, Bizkaia, Spain), belonging to the Gordón block of the Alén massif, subfossil shells of two unknown species have been found, one very large with an auriculate opening and a large parietal lamella, described as *I. goliath* Prieto & Gómez-Moliner n. sp., and another very small one with a circular opening and internally trilamellate, which is not described here. While the small species has been found alive in caves of this and other massifs, shells of *I. goliath* have only been found in the El Refugio caves, buried in consolidated clay. The age of these shells has not been determined, but we estimate it to be at least thousands of years old.

RESUMEN

El género *Iberozospeum* Jochum, Kneubühler, Prieto & Neubert, 2022 incluye nueve especies ibéricas, todas ellas vivientes y secuenciadas, aunque los análisis filogenéticos sugieren la existencia de más de 20 linajes potencialmente reconocibles taxonómicamente. Aparte de estas poblaciones, en la cueva de El Refugio-3 (Trucíos, Bizkaia, España), perteneciente al bloque de Gordón del macizo de Alén, se han localizado conchas subfósiles de dos especies inéditas, una muy grande con abertura auricular y una gran lamela parietal, que se describe como *I. goliath* Prieto & Gómez-Moliner n. sp., y otra muy pequeña de abertura circular y trilamelada internamente, que no se describe aquí. Mientras que la especie pequeña se ha encontrado, viviente, en cuevas de éste y otros macizos, las conchas de *I. goliath* se han encontrado únicamente en las cuevas de El Refugio,

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enterradas en arcilla consolidada. No se ha determinado la antigüedad de estas conchas, pero la estimamos en miles de años.

Key words: *Iberozospeum*, subfossil, new species, Biscay province, Gordón massif

Palabras clave: *Iberozospeum*, subfósil, nueva especie, Bizkaia, macizo de Gordón

INTRODUCTION

The subterranean genus *Zospeum* Bourguignat, 1856 encompasses a European radiation of terrestrial snails, although the Iberian species have recently been reclassified into a separate genus, *Iberozospeum* Jochum, Kneubühler, Prieto & Neubert, 2022. The Iberian radiation extends from the Pyrenees, where *I. bellesi* (GITTENBERGER, 1973) is endemic, to Asturias and northern León, with the remaining eight species distributed from east to west: *I. biscaiense* (Gómez & Prieto, 1985) and *I. vasconicum* (Prieto, De Winter, Weigand, Gómez & Jochum, 2015) in the Basque Country; *I. zaldívarae* (Prieto, De Winter, Weigand, Gómez & Jochum, 2015) in Sierra Salvada (Burgos/Álava); *I. costulatum* (Prieto & Jochum, 2022) in Cantabria/Bizkaia; *I. schaufussi* (Frauenfeld, 1862) in western Cantabria; and *I. percostulatum* (Alonso, Prieto, Quiñonero & Rolán, 2018), *I. gittenberg-eri* (Jochum, Prieto & De Winter, 2019), and *I. praetermissum* (Jochum, Prieto & De Winter, 2019) in eastern Asturias (ALONSO ET AL. 2018; GITTENBERGER 1973, 1980; GÓMEZ & PRIETO 1985; JOCHUM ET AL. 2015, 2019; KNEUBÜHLER ET AL. 2022).

The first molecular analysis of the genus (WEIGAND ET AL. 2013) revealed the existence of seven lineages among Cantabrian populations, three of which remain unnamed. A more recent study (KNEUBÜHLER ET AL. 2022) analyzed 57 Basque-Cantabrian populations using additional markers (COI, 16S, H3, ITS2), identifying 22 taxonomically recognizable lineages. While less than 130 caves containing *Iberozospeum* spp. have been cited in the literature, there are other 140 caves that have yielded new material of

Iberozospeum sp., indicating a significant potential for the discovery of new species. In many cases, this material includes fresh specimens that could potentially be analyzed genetically; however, in certain instances, the finding of live specimens has not been possible. Nevertheless, it is feasible to describe a species based on empty shells, which is common in malacological taxonomy, especially when the shells exhibit unique and distinctive characteristics. In this work, we describe a species that has been found exclusively within partially consolidated clay sediment in two closely located caves, and it is considered the first extinct species of the genus.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The studied shells were found embedded in consolidated clayey sediment. Although a shell was found on the surface on one occasion, the rest were obtained by surface excavation in a small accumulation of clayey soil containing fragments of concretion; the first shells were obtained by direct search, but it was more effective to extract several kilograms of clayey material and, in the laboratory, to obtain the shells by a careful washing and sifting process. The shells were found in two cavities situated opposite the village of Basinagre (Figure 1), but nestled in the western foothills of the small Gordón massif, which also belongs to the municipality of Trucíos (Bizkaia). The El Refugio cave, named for its use as a refuge during the Spanish Civil War, is located at the edge of the road; its

Figure 1. Type locality of *Iberozospeum goliath* n. sp. A: image of the Agüera River valley from the south (Google Earth); B: map (IGN) corresponding to that satellite image (dashed red line: Cantabria / Bizkaia border) together to (below left) a Spain map with Bizkaia in red and (below right) a physical map of Bizkaia showing the location (red symbol) of the area represented in the main map; C: drone image of the location of the El Refugio-1 cave (right circle) and El Refugio-3 cave (left circle) cave, this one 5 m above the kilometer point 44. Photo: J. Moreno.

Figura 1. Localidad tipo de Iberozospeum goliath n. sp. A: imagen del valle del río Agüera desde el sur (Google Earth); B: mapa (IGN) correspondiente a dicha imagen de satélite (línea discontinua roja: frontera Cantabria / Bizkaia) junto a (abajo a la izquierda) un mapa de España con Bizkaia en rojo y (abajo a la derecha) un mapa físico de Bizkaia que muestra la localización (símbolo rojo) del área representada en el mapa principal; C: imagen de dron de la localización de la cueva El Refugio-1 (círculo derecho) y la cueva El Refugio-3 (círculo izquierdo), esta última a 5 m sobre el punto kilométrico 44. Foto: J. Moreno.

entrance gives access to a chamber, from which two galleries almost filled with clayey material start, in which a seasonal stream emerges that drains into the Agüera river. From the bottom of the gallery on the right, where a shell was found on soil surface, a cat flap gives access to an interior gallery traversed by the aforementioned stream that siphons off a few hundred meters below. On the other hand, the El Refugio-3 cave, located 30 m to the north and 5 m above the road (Figures 1C, 2), is a completely fossil cavity and its development barely reaches 25 m in length; a descending gallery, bordered on the left by an accumulation of rock blocks (behind which there is a small, low-height room), allows access to the bottom at a distance of about 10 m after a slight bend to the left with a cut of barely 1 m. The clayey material containing the subfossil shells is found below and among the blocks that form the bend. About 10 m to the right of this cavity is the El Refugio-2 cave, with a low-height entrance leading to a wide chamber from whose bottom small, short galleries start; no *Iberozospeum* shells have been found in this fossil cavity.

Shells were measured, drawn and photographed using a Nikon SMZ-1500 stereomicroscope implemented with a Leica camera and a morphometric analysis system; mensuration of ten paratypes at CSQ was conducted (courtesy of Sergio Quiñonero-Salgado) using Adobe Photoshop on photographs scaled with a millimetric slide. Series of photographs were stacked with the Helicon Focus 8 software, and the graph was generated with PAST 4.17 software. The SEM photograph in Fig. 4A was

taken using a Hitachi S-3400N Scanning Electron Microscope from the Analytical and High-Resolution Microscopy Service in Biomedicine, of the University of the Basque Country (EHU-UPV). The SEM photographs in Fig. 5A-B (courtesy of JGM Raven) were taken without coating in a JEOL-IT510 LV using low vacuum, 10 KV voltage and 30 Pa pressure. The composite image of the El Refugio-3 cave consist on a point cloud created with the LiDAR scanner of an Iphone 13 Pro and obtained through the Scaniverse program, which was subsequently processed using the CloudCompare software.

Morphometric parameters (Shell height, Shell width, Last whorl height, Aperture height and Aperture width) were measured as described by INÄBNIT ET AL. (2019: Fig.2). The number of whorls was counted following the methodology of Kerney & Cameron (1979). Nomenclature of dentition and lamellae follows the proposed by INÄBNIT ET AL. (2019): only two lamellae may be seen in the aperture: the parietalis (which extends inward on the columella) and the columellaris (which extends inward on the lower part of the columella), but a supraparietalis lamella may be in the roof of the body whorl (beneath the preceding whorl). Two teeth can be present in the aperture: the angularis on the parietal side, to the right of the parietalis, and the palatalis on the palatal side of the aperture.

Abbreviations

CAA: Álvaro Alonso Collection (Gijón, Spain);
CHR: Han Raven collection (The Hague, The Netherlands);

(Right page) Figure 2. Type locality of *Iberozospeum goliath* n. sp. A: entrance to El Refugio-3 cave (the small yellow/green bar on the right is 15 cm long); B: composite image of the floor plan of the cavity (yellow star, site); C: topography of the cavity. Note that the most inner part of the cave is not planned. Photo, C. Prieto; composite image and topography, J. Moreno.

(Página derecha) Figura 2. Localidad tipo de *Iberozospeum goliath* n. sp. A: entrada a la cueva El Refugio-3 (la pequeña barra amarilla/verde de la derecha tiene 15 cm de longitud); B: imagen compuesta de la planta de la cavidad (estrella amarilla, yacimiento); C: topografía de la cavidad. Nótese que la parte más interna de la cueva no está planificada. Foto, C. Prieto; imagen compuesta y topografía, J. Moreno.

A

B

C

CJRC: Jesús Ruiz-Cobo Collection (Santander, Spain);
CSQ: Sergio Quiñonero Collection (l'Hospitalet de Llobregat, Spain);
MNCN, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales (Madrid, Spain);

RMNH: Rijksmuseum van Natuurlijke Historie collection, Naturalis (Leiden, The Netherlands);
ZUPV: Cave Fauna Collection, Department of Zoology of the University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU).

TAXONOMY

Class GASTROPODA

Order ELLOBIIDA

Family ELLOBIIDAE L. Pfeiffer, 1854

Genus *Iberozospeum* Jochum, Kneubühler, Prieto & Neubert, 2022

Iberozospeum goliath Prieto & Gómez n. sp. (Figs. 3-5)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:BD48AD4D-56F1-4F64-9E5F-91910B8CB70A

Zospeum sp. nov. 2: ALTONAGA ET AL. 1994: 72

Type material. Holotype • 1 shell; province of Bizkaia, Trucíos municipality, Basinagre village, El Refugio-3 Cave; 43.28316°N -3.25842°W; 18 Feb 2018; C. Prieto leg.; MNCN: 15.05/200557 ex-ZUPV-5117. Paratypes • 4 shells (2 shells, Fig. 4E-F: 1 shell, Fig. 4D); same locality as for holotype; 30 Dec 1985; B. Gómez & C. Prieto leg.; ZUPV-116, ZUPV-117 • 4 shells; same locality as for holotype; 26 Jan 1986; B. Gómez & C. Prieto leg.; ZUPV-123 • 1 shell; same locality as for holotype; 17 Jun 2011; C. Prieto, B. Gómez, A. Jochum, A. Weigand & R. Slapnik leg.; ZUPV-543 • 36 shells; same locality as for holotype; 18 Feb 2018; C. Prieto leg.; ZUPV-5117: 17, MNCN 15.05/200558: 10, CSQ: 3, CAA: 3, CJRC: 3 • 31 shells (Fig. 5); same locality as for holotype; 6 Sep 2023; C. Prieto, S. Quiñonero & J.G.M. Raven leg.; CSQ: 10; CHR-L3242: 19; RMNH.MOL.350860: 2 • 1 shell; Basque Country, province of Bizkaia, Trucíos municipality, Basinagre village, El Refugio Cave; 43.28287°N, 3.25840°W; 140 m asl; 8 Mar 1981; B. Gómez & C. Prieto leg.; ZUPV-29.

Derivatio nominis. The name is derived from Goliath (noun in apposition), referring to a biblical Philistine warrior giant who was defeated and killed by the young David. The analogy serves to emphasize that the other species of *Iberozospeum* found at the type locality, an unnamed and the smallest species of the genus on the other hand, is still extant while the large species is presumably extinct.

Type locality: SPAIN; Basque Country, province of Bizkaia, Trucíos municipality, Basinagre village, El Refugio-3 Cave; 43.28316°N -3.25842°W; 145 m asl.

Diagnosis: This species is distinguished from all species of the genus *Iberozospeum* by its large shell (height ≥ 1.9 mm), thin and regularly ribbed, an auriciform opening with a wide parietal

callus and two lamellae at the aperture of shell, a large parietal one and a small columellar one visible obliquely.

Description: High conical shell (up to 1.5 times its width), with 5.5-6 very

(Right page) Figure 3. *Iberozospeum goliath* n. sp. Holotype shell, 2.245 mm height, El Refugio-3 Cave, Basinagre, Trucíos, Bizkaia, Basque Country, Spain (MNCN-15.05/200557, ex ZUPV-5117). A: spiral view; B: umbilical view; C: frontal view; D: oblique apertural view; E: lateral view.

(Página derecha) Figura 3. *Iberozospeum goliath* n. sp. Holotipo, 2,245 mm de altura, Cueva El Refugio-3, Basinagre, Trucíos, Bizkaia, País Vasco, España (MNCN-15.05/200557, ex ZUPV-5117). A: vista apical; B: vista umbilical; C: vista frontal; D: vista apertural oblicua; E: vista lateral.

convex whorls and deep sutures. Last whorl somewhat higher than half shell height (59-62%), with a rounded carinal edge situated in an upper position; final part of the last whorl ascending, reaching the carinal line at the aperture. Narrow umbilical depression with closed umbilicus. Aperture auriculiform with vertical columellar edge, well curved base and palatal edge, with the upper end joined perpendicularly to the shell. Peristome reflected and thickened, more prominently towards the basal area, with the marginal edges joined by a thick and wide parietal callosity; in lateral view, the upper half of the opening is almost vertical while the lower is more inclined backwards, with the transition marked by respective bulges of the columellar and palatal edges. Aperture with two lamellae, a parietalis located near the parieto-columellar corner, strong and elevated, inclined to the right side and running one complete whorl inward from the plane of the opening; and a columellaris wide and low, immersed, not surpassing the columella, but clearly visible at the

appropriate angle, running $\frac{3}{4}$ of a whorl inward. Protoconch formed by $1\frac{1}{2}$ whorls, smooth, without microperforations; teleoconch covered by numerous longitudinal ribs (more than 100 in the penultimate whorl), continuous from suture to suture and crossed by a faint spiral microcostulation.

Dimensions of the holotype (mm): shell height, 2.246; shell width, 1.554; last whorl height, 1.284; aperture height, 1.117; aperture width, 0.928.

Variability: Based on measurements of shells (Table I), the variability of conchological parameters is very low, as indicated by the coefficient of variation values, ranging from 3.53% for the number of whorls and 4.10% for shell width to 6.6% for aperture height and width. Regarding the apertural formations, the parietal lamella is always well developed but the columellar lamella may be reduced to the extent of being nearly imperceptible from the outside, although it is always present internally.

Geographical distribution: This species is only found in the small karst block of Gordón (Trucíos, Bizkaia).

DISCUSSION

Iberozospeum goliath n. sp. is an unmistakable species; none of the known species of the genus reaches a size of 2 mm (Figure 6), with *I. percostulatum* being the only species in which some shells reach a height of 1.8 mm, although the average height is 1.54 mm (ALONSO ET AL. 2017). The smallest specimens of *I. praetermissum*, the smallest described species of the genus, do not exceed 1 mm in height (having a

volume of less than 0.25 mm³) so the shells of *I. goliath* are twice as long (with an average volume seven times greater). The shell size record for the Alpine-Dinarian genus *Zospeum* is held by an Italian shell of *Z. spelaenum* (Rossmässler, 1839) reaching 2.62 mm (PEZZOLI 1982, INÄBNIT ET AL. 2019), although both the smallest and average sizes of this species (1.49 and 1.962 mm) are smaller than the corresponding measurements

(Right page) Figure 4. *Iberozospeum goliath* n. sp. Paratype shells. A: 2.07 mm (ZUPV.123); B: 1.93 mm (ZUPV.5117); C: 2.05 mm (ZUPV.5117); D: 2.12 mm height (ZUPV.117); E, F: 2.1 mm (ZUPV.116; both currently broken above the body whorl); G: 2.03 mm (ZUPV.5117); H: protoconch of the holotype (the arrowhead points transition to teleoconch).

(Página derecha) Figura 4. *Iberozospeum goliath* n. sp. Conchas paratípicas. A: 2,07 mm (ZUPV.123); B: 1,93 mm (ZUPV.5117); C: 2,05 mm (ZUPV.5117); D: 2,12 mm de altura (ZUPV.117); E, F: 2,1 mm (ZUPV.116; ambas actualmente rotas por encima de la última vuelta); G: 2,03 mm (ZUPV.5117); H: protoconcha del holotipo (la punta de flecha señala la transición a la teleoconcha).

Figure 5. *Iberozospeum goliath* n. sp. SEM photographs of a paratype (Naturalis). A: lateral view of the protoconch and first whorl of the teleoconch (the arrowhead points transition to teleoconch); B: detail of the protoconch surface; C: partial lateral view of the spire. Photos, Han Raven.

Figura 5. *Iberozospeum goliath* n. sp. Fotografías SEM de un paratipo (Naturalis). A: vista lateral de la protoconcha y primer verticilo de la teleoconcha (la punta de flecha señala la transición a la teleoconcha); B: detalle de la superficie de la protoconcha; C: vista lateral parcial de la espira. Fotos, Han Raven.

of *I. goliath* (1.93 and 2.143). *Z. costatum* (Freyer, 1855), with a size range of 1.86–2.22 mm, is the only Alpine-Dinarian species whose average size barely reaches 2 mm.

Regarding shell sculpture, only two other species exhibit conspicuous costulation, *I. costulatum* and *I. percostulatum*, but the ribs in these species are stronger and more separated out, with less than 30 ribs on the last whorl of *I. costulatum* and approximately 50 on that of *I. percostulatum* (ALONSO ET AL. 2018; KNEUBÜHLER ET AL. 2022). Regarding the apertural formations, only two other species have structures on the parietal surface, but those are shorter: two short but tall lamellae in *I. biscaiense* and a punctate thickening in *I. zaldivarae* (GÓMEZ & PRIETO 1985; JOCHUM ET AL. 2015).

However, the species most similar to *I. goliath* is the Slovenian *Zospeum frauenfeldi* (Freyer, 1855), with which it

shares the large size, auricular shape of the aperture, arrangement of the apertural formations and complete costulation of the shell. Judging from the figures of BOLE (1974), the main differences from that species lie in the greater height of the parietal lamella, the shorter path of the lamellae towards the interior, the shorter distance between the suture and the aperture, the upper position of the maximum diameter and the presence of spiral microcostulation. Given that these two species belong to different genera, it can be inferred that the similarities of their shells are homoplastic.

In the Trucíos municipality there are two calcareous Urganian massifs separated by the Agüera river, which runs from south to north through the municipality, with the Jorrios massif located to the west and the Gordón blocks to the east (Figure 1). The Jorrios massif, extending further north into the neighboring

Table I. Main parameters and statistics of shells of *Iberozospeum goliath* n. sp. (first five in mm).
 Table I. Parámetros principales y estadísticas de las conchas de *Iberozospeum goliath* n. sp. (cinco primeros en mm).

	Shell height	Shell width	Last wh. height	Aperture height	Aperture width	No. of whorls	Shell h./shell w.	Last wh.h./shell h.
Average (n=43)	2.175	1.515	1.317	1.068	0.923	5.700	1.437	0.595
Minimum	1.932	1.386	1.169	0.892	0.800	5.300	1.312	0.539
Maximum	2.380	1.640	1.510	1.210	1.030	6.100	1.601	0.644
Standard deviation	0.109	0.062	0.087	0.071	0.056	0.201	0.073	0.022
Variation coefficient	5.017	4.102	6.634	6.624	6.069	3.529	5.061	3.695

municipality of Guriezo (Cantabria) and having an area of about 18 km² (G.E.V. 1980), is very poorly sampled and *Iberozospeum* sp. has only been discovered in two cavities; in both cases it was an unnamed species resembling the Asturian *I. praetermissum* albeit with excessively developed inner lamellae (unpublished data). The Gordón blocks (Figure 7) represent the western foothills of the Alén massif, which extends to the north of the municipalities of Artzentales and Sopuerta and encompassing four small limestone patches (G.E.V. 1984). The cavities within the northern Gordón block, which lithologically extends from the Jorrios massif, have limited significance and none have been biologically sampled, although they include the Cueva La Mora spring, a flooded chasm that has been dived to a depth of 111 m (<https://www.prodi-tech.es/exploracion-cueva-la-mora/>) and serves as the outflow for the Jorrios massif (G.E.V. 1980).

The southern Gordón block, separated from the northern block by a narrow strip of dark sandy marls, comprises impure Paraurgonian limestones (G.E.V. 1984). It also has minor cavities, with only three exceeding 100 m in length; aside from El Refugio caves, only two other cavities of this block, Torca de la Campa Loredó of 275 m length and Torca de la Peña Loredó of 143 m length, have been biologically explored (unpublished data) in attempts to find living individuals of *I. goliath* n. sp. The already cited unnamed *Iberozospeum* species from

the Jorrios massif was found in the four caves, while *I. goliath* was only found in the El Refugio caves. Shells of the unnamed species were found in the typical habitat of the genus, leading to the inference that it is extant, as confirmed by the recent discovery of live specimens during a visit on January 19, 2025, to the El Refugio-1 cave. In the case of *I. goliath*, most shells were found embedded in compacted clay soil from the El Refugio-3 cave, except for a single shell retrieved from the clay soil of a gallery in the El Refugio-1 cave; this shell, with an aged appearance (with a mottled coloration due to manganese oxide) is believed to have been displaced or exposed by re-excavation of the sediment. In the El Refugio-1 cave there are thick accumulations of clayey material that have not been explored in search of *I. goliath* shells, although we assume they have a more recent origin because they are found in an active cavity.

Since the first record, *Z. schaufussi* from an unidentified cave in northern Spain (VON FRAUENFELD 1862), fewer than 130 caves containing *Iberozospeum* spp. have been documented in the literature focusing on the Iberian species (GITTENBERGER 1973, 1980, GÓMEZ & PRIETO 1985, PRIETO & GÓMEZ 1985, ESCOLÀ & BECH 1986, DUPRÉ 1991, ALTONAGA ET AL. 1994, JOCHUM ET AL. 2012, 2015, ALONSO ET AL. 2018, PRIETO & ZUAZU 2018, PRIETO, AZKOAGA & EXPÓSITO 2019, KNEUBÜHLER ET AL. 2022). However, there are another 140 caves in the Cantabrian-Pyrenean region

Figure 6. 3D graph of the main morphological features of the shell (shell height, shell width and body whorl height) of *Iberozospeum* species. Black dots, *I. goliath* (red diamond: holotype); coloured dots, other *Iberozospeum* spp. Dot colours follow the colour assigned to *Iberozospeum* clades recognized by KNEUBÜHLER ET AL. (2022). Morphometric data of other *Iberozospeum* spp. from publications cited in the literature but other are inedit data.

Figura 6. Gráfico 3D de las principales características morfológicas de la concha (altura de la concha, ancho de la concha y altura de la última vuelta) de especies de *Iberozospeum*. Puntos negros, *I. goliath* (cubo rojo: holotipo); puntos de colores, otras especies de *Iberozospeum*. Los colores de los puntos siguen el color asignado a los clados de *Iberozospeum* reconocidos por KNEUBÜHLER ET AL. (2022). Los datos morfométricos de otras especies de *Iberozospeum* provienen de las publicaciones citadas en la literatura, pero otros son inéditos.

where empty shells or live snails of the genus *Iberozospeum* have been discovered by the authors, or by colleagues and friends, and deposited in the ZUPV collection. The expertise acquired in the detection and gathering of *Iberozospeum* over 45 years of biospeleological sampling, along with the distinctiveness provided by the large shells of *I. goliath*, makes it highly unlikely that this species could have gone unnoticed, being present in its characteristic

habitat, while specimens of other, much smaller species were found.

The age of the subfossil shells of *I. goliath* is yet to be determined. The site is located within a small, entirely fossil cavity, showing no signs of recent water activity, and beneath and among detached blocks of the roof lacking stalagmitic crust. The cavity opens into impure Paraurgonian limestone, which is highly fragmented and fissured, as is evident both at the entrance and on the inner

Figure 7. A: aerial view (Google Earth) of the Gordón karstic area from the West with the location of the known karstic cavities (numbers are catalogue codes cited by G.E.V. (1984, 1985), other alphanumeric codes are for posteriorly discovered caves); B: lithological map of the same area (<https://www.geo.euskadi.eus/geobisorea>). Symbols, Red triangle: El Refugio caves; Shell: biologically sampled cave; Water waves: cave spring.

Figura 7. A: vista aérea (Google Earth) del área kárstica de Gordón desde el oeste con la localización de las cavidades kársticas conocidas (los números son códigos de catálogo citados por G.E.V. (1984, 1985), otros códigos alfanuméricos son cuevas descubiertas posteriormente); B: mapa litológico de la misma zona (<https://www.geo.euskadi.eus/geobisorea>). Símbolos, Triángulo rojo: cuevas de El Refugio; Concha: cueva muestreada biológicamente; Ondas de agua: cueva surgente.

walls. It is plausible that the entrance, displaying drill marks from dynamite holes, was created during rock blasting

for road construction. The compacted clay forming the deposit also contained shells of other cave-dwelling species

(the small *Iberozospeum* mentioned earlier, *Cryptazeca vasconica* (Kobelt, 1884) and two indetermined *Alzoniella* spp.) along with a few shells of *Discus rotundatus* (Müller, 1774), *Elona quimperiana* (Férussac, 1821), *Oxychilus navarricus* (Bourguignat, 1870) and *Acicula fusca* (Montagu, 1803), although these may have recently fallen on the deposit (Sergio Quiñonero-Salgado and Han Raven, pers. comm.). Likely the clay is of Late Pleistocene (last interglacial or glacial) or early Holocene age.

According to BOLE (1974), the most taxonomically relevant conchological characters for the Alpine-Dinarian *Zospeum* are the shape of the opening, the presence and arrangement of internal lamellae and apertural teeth. Considering the morphology of the shell, species of *Iberozospeum* can be divided into three groups:

1. ventrude shell, with an auriculi-form aperture and formations on the parietal side of the aperture; includes *I. biscaiense* and *I. zaldívarae*.

2. medium-sized shell, with an oblique oval aperture and wide parietal callosity; includes *I. bellesi*, *I. percostulatum*, *I. gittenbergeri* and *I. costulatum*, the latter with a robust columellar lamella.

3. small and slender shell, with circular aperture, continuous peristome with thickened parietal edge, and three lamellae (one or two columellar lamellae inside, and sometimes a third in the roof of the body whorl); includes *I. schaufussi*, *I. praetermissum* and *I. vasconicum*, the latter with only a single columellar lamella.

Comparing this conchological classification with the phylogenetic scheme obtained by KNEUBÜHLER ET AL. (2022), no obvious correlation is observed

except for the basal clade that includes *I. biscaiense*, *I. zaldívarae* and a third lineage corresponding to an unpublished species from the Sierra de Aralar, which has a shell similar to that of *I. zaldívarae* (unpubl. observ.). KNEUBÜHLER ET AL. (2022) also obtain a more derived clade formed by *I. schaufussi* and three “vasconicum” subclades (termed brown, pink and blue) that hides at least six unpublished species, all of them with shells of the group 3; *I. praetermissum* does not belong to this clade but fits within a set of three clades that includes the species of group 2. Based on the shape of the aperture and the presence of formations in the parietal shield, it is considered that *I. goliath* would fall into group 1, leading to the conclusion that it would be part of the most basal clade of *Iberozospeum*.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

To Han Raven for providing relevant SEM photographs of the protoconch and the costulation of a paratype from the Naturalis collection and to Sergio Quiñonero-Salgado for the morphometric data of the paratypes housed in his collection; and to both for critical reading of previous versions of the manuscript. To Jon Fernández and Alfonso Calvo for their help and collaboration in the samplings carried out at Torca de la Campa Loredo and Torca de la Peña Loredo. To the Department of Zoology and Animal Cell Biology (Faculty of Science and Technology, University of the Basque Country) for permission to use the Nikon SMZ-1500 stereomicroscope and its Nikon DS5M camera implemented with an image analysis software.

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